

RELIGION AND MEDIA: VALUE TRANSFORMERS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Values are essential ingredients in determining the actions and activities in any human society. The level of morality in a society is directly related to the cherished values in such society. Therefore, an amoral society is where values are broken down and the common good is not cultivated by both the leaders and followers. Religion and media have been presented as important instruments in building and promoting values. Before the arrival of foreign religion and western education the people of Nigeria believed in the gods that would not allow amoral behaviours. Information went to the people from the community leaders (kings and chiefs). It was the belief in the gods or deities and the trust in the information from the leaders that shaped the values of the people. In the civilized era, traditional belief system had been replaced with foreign religions—majorly Christianity and Islam—and the local transmission of information has been substituted with media. In the case of the present Nigeria, evidences show that there is a breakdown of values and the common good is no longer preached nor lived by people. The values and morality that were practiced before have been influenced by the processes of modernity that are passing through the nation. This breakdown of values could not be without religion and media roles as the vanguard of helping people to build positive orientation which leads to good character. Every religion and media encourage values and moral society but in the situation where religion and media are compromised, values are broken in the society. The study used documentary design of qualitative research approach consulting plethora of sources, including journal articles and books to explore the function of religion and media in transforming values in Nigeria. The study indicated that for the ideal values to be cherished in Nigeria, religious groups and media need to stop promoting immoral behaviours but promote values that can change the country from her negative to positive image.

Keywords: value transformation, religion and media, amoral society, building and promoting, positive orientation

INTRODUCTION

Value is sometimes synonymous to morality and is important in any society. When positive values are cherished and imbibed by a society, it paves the way for understanding, cooperation, peace, and development. A society without positive values can be beset with myriad of ills,

such as hatred, insecurity, corruption, and lack of development (Obasola, 2015). Positive value is closely related to religion. Religion is a concept of believing in a higher being or power and because of that belief, people seek and live by a set of positive values so as not to offend the higher being. Religion is generally a binding force, creating a common ground which promotes peace and development. The propagation of religion and positive values requires the use of media as a strong means of educating and enlightening people on the kind of life they are to live and the right values to imbibe. Media has been used in many societies to promote and educate people on diverse aspects of human life be it moral, education, health, religion, politics, and development.

Nigeria is a religious nation with three major religious groups—Christianity, Islam and African Traditional Religion (Afolabi, 2015; Odey & Ashipu, 2020). The role of these religions is to promote positive values. Therefore, Nigeria is expected to be a nation saturated with the awareness and practice of positive values. The media play a significant role in creating in creating such awareness and there are many media houses—print, radio, and television—in Nigeria. In addition to these, many people use social media for different purposes with majority using it for information and entertainment. The purpose of media is to expose ill-factors in the society and promote values and development. But studies (Eboreime, 2008, Kadiri, Muhammed, Raji, & Sulaiman, 2015), daily news, and experiences indicate that Nigeria is plagued with incidences of ill-value which indicates the need for value transformation.

The study adopted documentary design of qualitative approach to investigate the roles of religion and media in transforming values in Nigeria. Many documents in form of book, journal articles in hard-copy, soft-copy and on the Internet were consulted in order to reach a decisive and objective conclusion based on which recommendations were made.

CONCEPT OF VALUE

Value is a standard or ideal with which actions, people, things, or situation is evaluated. Value can be personal which is standard of things, behaviour or situation endorsed by an individual. It determines moral right or wrong. Value is a basic and fundamental belief that guides or motivates attitudes or actions. In other words, value is that which is good, desirable, and/or worthwhile. It is the motive behind purposeful action (Cambridge Dictionary, 2020; Mintz, 2018; Obasola, 2015). They determine the priorities and are the measures used to indicate if life is going the way someone desires it to go.

People feel satisfied and content when what they do and the way they behave match their values. When considered from the angle of various disciplines, value is always used in reference to moral ideas, general orientation towards interest, attitude, preferences, needs, sentiments and dispositions. Value determines the acceptable behaviour in a given society (Eluu, 2016). Individual's disposition and approach to wealth, loyalty, equality, justice, integrity, truth, fraternity, friendliness, and hard-work are based on such individual's value orientation. What is desirable to a person is determined by the values upheld and there are varied degree to which each person values one thing above the other. Individual achievement, happiness, and level of materialism are evidences of a person's values (Mintz, 2018).

Socially shared and intensely felt values are a fundamental part of people's lives as these values become part of their personalities. Such values are shared and reinforced by those with whom individuals interact. Values may change with time within individual or culture due to enlightenment, education, and/or experience. Since values often strongly influence both attitude and behaviour, they serve as a kind of personal compass for conduct in places—

workplace, religious gathering, meetings, homes—where people find themselves. The followings is a list of some characteristics of as postulated by iEduNote (2020).

- 1 Values are practical, and valuation requires not just techniques but also an understanding of the strategic context.
- 2 They can provide standards of competence and morality.
- 3 They can go beyond specific situations or persons.
- 4 Personal values can be influenced by culture, tradition, education, religion and a combination of internal and external factors.
- 5 They are relatively permanent.
- 6 They are more central to the core of a person.
- 7 Many of the core values for individuals are learned early in life from family, friends, neighbourhood, school, the mass print, visual media and other sources within the society.
- 8 Values are loaded with effective thoughts about ideas, objects, behaviour, etc.
- 9 Values contain a judgmental element in that they carry an individual's ideas as to what is right, good, or desirable.
- 10 Values may differ from culture to culture and person to person.
- 11 Values play a significant role in the integration and fulfilment of someone's basic impulses and desire stably and consistently appropriate for his or her living.
- 12 They are generic experiences in social action made up of both individual and social responses and attitudes.
- 13 They build up societies, integrate social relations.
- 14 They mould the ideal dimensions of personality and depth of culture.
- 15 They influence people's behaviour and serve as criteria for evaluating the actions of others.
- 16 And they have a great role to play in the conduct of social life. They help in creating norms to guide day-to-day behaviour.

Types of Values

There are two broad types of values (iEduNote, 2020): terminal values and instrumental values. Terminal values are values that are taught to be more important or desirable. They refer to desirable end-states of existence, the goals a person would like to achieve during his or her lifetime. They include happiness, self-respect, recognition, inner harmony, leading a prosperous life, fulfilment and professional excellence. Instrumental values on the other hand deal with views on acceptable modes of conduct as means of achieving the terminal values. These include being honest, sincere, ethical, courageous, peaceful, wise, and being ambitious. These values are more focused on personality traits and character (Hills, 2002). The following table gives the description of the two types of values.

Table 1: *Types of Values* (Adapted from iEduNote, 2020)

Terminal Values	Instrumental Values
A comfortable life (a prosperous life)	Ambitious (hardworking)
An exciting life (a stimulating, active life)	Broadminded (open-minded)
A sense of accomplishment (lasting contribution)	Capable (competent, efficient)
A world of peace (free of war and conflict)	Cheerful (light-hearted, joyful)
A world of beauty (the beauty of nature and the arts)	Clean (neat, tidy)
Equality (brotherhood, equal opportunity for all)	Courageous (standing up for your beliefs)
Family security (taking care of loved ones)	Forgiving (willing to pardon)
Freedom (independence, free choice)	Helpful (working for the welfare of others)
Happiness (contentedness)	Honest (sincere, truthful)
Inner harmony (freedom from inner conflict)	Imaginative (daring, creative)
Mature love (sexual and spiritual intimacy)	Independent (self-reliant, self-sufficient)
National security (protection from attack)	Intellectual (intelligent, reflective)
Pleasure (an enjoyable, leisurely life)	Logical (consistent, rational)
Salvation (saved, eternal)	Loving (affectionate, tender)
Self-respect (self-esteem)	Obedient (dutiful, respectful)
Social recognition (respect, admiration)	Polite (courteous, well-mannered)
A true friend (close companionship)	Responsible (dependable, reliable)
Wisdom (a mature understanding of life)	Self-controlled (restrained, self-disciplined)

Sources of values

Values are acquired from different sources beginning from when a person is born. Each of the sources determines what a person adopts and maintains as his or her values in life. Some of the sources of values include family, friends and peers, community or society, school, relatives, organization, history, books, religion and media (iEduNote, 2020). This study focuses on religion and media as the sources of values.

VALUES IN NIGERIAN SOCIETIES

Some of the core values in Nigeria, according to New Nigeria Foundation (2020), include transparency and accountability. Nigerians are expected to be open, frank and honest in communications, transactions and operations. They are to demonstrate responsibility for their actions by explaining, clarifying and justifying whatever they do. Another core value in Nigeria is professionalism. Nigerians are to demonstrate competence that is evidenced in quality

output, strict adherence to professional and ethical standards, principles, and courtesy when dealing with others. Integrity is another core value expected to be upheld by Nigerians. By this, they are to have sound moral and ethical principles, and be upright, honest and sincere in all their dealings, even when no one is watching. Another core value in Nigerian societies is respect for diversity. Nigerians are to recognize, understand and accept that each individual is unique and they are to value the differences and ensure that everyone is treated fairly and equally in a safe, conducive and nurturing environment. Teamwork is the fifth core value in Nigeria according to New Nigeria Foundation (2020). With this, Nigerians are expected to work together cohesively towards a common goal, create a conducive atmosphere for work, acquiescent personal prominence and support each other to achieve the common good.

Looking at the situation in Nigeria, according to Olaito (2017), in most cases, many Nigerians do not recognize or hold to these values. There are hardly any communal systems to which people are accountable in any respect to such societal values. Honesty is hard to come by, opulence and avarice are used to acquire that which should be given by character merit. In Nigeria, the issues of honesty, meritocracy, hard work, mindfulness, respect for others, and putting the common interest first are not being considered nor settled (Obasola, 2015). What is often seen on display in Nigeria is selfishness, dishonesty and insincerity. Nigeria needs a transformation of values because the core societal values seem to be directly opposite to people's—including leaders—beliefs and practices. The values that were formerly cherished in Nigeria are almost in the threshold of extinction and the nation is in moral crisis (Egbule, 2019; Enu & Esu, 2011; Odey & Ashipu, 2020). There is a need for a deliberate entrenchment of the values into the consciousness of the people (Njoku, 2015; Obasola, 2015).

RELIGION AND ITS ROLE IN VALUE TRANSFORMATION IN NIGERIA

Religion is derived from the Latin word *re* meaning again and *ligae* meaning tie or bind (Adetunji, 2012; Iwuoha, 2014; Odiba, 2002; Wulff, 1997). These two words suggest the idea of restoring. Restoration in this context has to do with the relationship between humans and God in the one hand and between humans and their environment on the other hand. Religion is a phenomenon of norms, beliefs and practices that determine how humans relate with God and one another. It is about doing good or what is right believing that God will give reward (Agbiji & Swart, 2015; Azuakor, 2019). Religion, by its nature, is concerned with dimension of values that transcends mundane reality; it is a strong and institutionalized measure that can transform values (Obey & Ashipu, 2020; Wulff, 1997).

Religion is to bring human society into conformity with its ideal and practices which it projects to be right and of value (Iwuoha, 2014). And society is recognized by the values it espouses. Therefore, religion is to transform the society from evil to good by teaching the right value and by orientating people to admire and imbibe positive values (Agbiji & Swart, 2015; Azuakor, 2019). It is to foster unity and love. Religion is to have influence on every aspect of national engagement such as politics, education, economic, and morality (Nath, 2015; Nwaomah, 2012; Olaore, 2012) while at the same time promoting humanitarian activities such as charitable hospitals, schools, homes for the homeless, orphanages, care for the poor (Nath, 2015). Religion takes an important place when it comes to establishing regular order in the society. It helps to shape the character of individuals thereby moulding the social life of people. Through its cherished values, religion teaches and engraves obedience, virtue, justice, equality and dignity, love, respect, sanctity of human life, service to humanity, and moral consciousness in the minds of people. It enforces good behaviour and strengthens social solidarity and stabilizes social order. Religion fosters patriotic sentiments and maintain social integration. It gives meaning to life (Agbaji & Swart, 2015; Nath, 2015, Zed, 2017). According to Nath (2015),

religion is the discipline which touches the conscience and helps to struggle with evil and sordidness. It saves from greed, lust and hatred, restores values and transforms people in a society.

Spread across three major religious groups, Nigerians have been considered to be notoriously religious (Abolarin & Adeleye, 2019; Adetunji, 2012) with ten to twelve religious related public holidays annually (Adetunji, 2012). There is no time both night and day throughout the year when Nigerians are not engaged in one form of worship or another, whether in church, mosque, prayer ground or prayer mountain (except for this time of ongoing Covid-19 pandemic). A surprising number of alternatives to public worship as well as several clever antics have emerged in response to the lockdown and restriction policies of both Federal and state governments. The creative and tenacity demonstrated in these alternatives have further demonstrated the high level of religiosity among Nigerians. These many worship times give opportunities for religion to transform the nation. Through the religions, values are to be taught and ingrained in people's mind so much so that their behaviours effortlessly reflect such values.

Instead of teaching and promoting values, religions especially Christianity and Islam, through their leaders have destroyed the cherished values in Nigeria (Abolarin & Adeleye, 2019; Agbiji & Swart, 2015; Alufohai, 2017; Ezekwesili, 2015; Manala, 2013). Adetunji (2012), stated that although many Nigerians profess religion, they lack the transformation that should accompany experiential knowledge of true religion. The lack of transformation is indicated by unrestrained love of money, bribery and corruption, moral degeneration of the law enforcement agents, destruction of educational standard, killings, absence of love in the society, oppression, and total breakdown of morality (Adetunji, 2012; Azuakor, 2019; Obasola, 2015). Religion has been used to promote and enrich self rather than building societal values. Some religious leaders patronize corrupt political leaders to satisfy their greed, lust for money and material gains and religion has been politicized. Religion is being used to induce ethnicity, violence, corruption, hatred and killing (Iwuoha, 2014). Religious leaders no longer admonish their followers to embrace morality and values since they themselves no longer uphold such. And any religion that fails to propagate peace and values remains inimical to the sustainability of society (Agbiji & Swart, 2015; Iwuoha, 2014). Religion, pathetically, has failed in its roles as value transformer in Nigeria.

ROLES OF MEDIA IN VALUE TRANSFORMATION

Presently, media is everything (Koch, 2013; Sharma, Sharma & Rawat, 2015) be it printed paper, digital data, television news, blogs, email newsletters, iPhone app alerts, Facebook updates, text messages, tweets etc. Media provides news and information, influences decisions, changes public opinions, shapes attitudes and values, sets agenda, and gives the society what to think about. Since values are shaped by structural and cultural forces such as social class and occupational positions, cultural worldviews, individual cultural orientations, the media plays the role of providing education that will inform and influence the forces (Firat, 2014). Fiat (2014), further found that media usage is related to value orientations in ways that change people's life. According to him, entertainment and political media are negatively related to value orientation. Media are to instill social trust, honesty, accountability, peaceful coexistence, and courage in people's orientation.

Ideally, people build their opinions, attitudes and behaviours based on the information from media (Tsfati & Cohen, 2013). For media to achieve their goal of transforming values, there is a need to build trust, be objective in their coverage, avoid favouritism—to make people have positive perception, and make people believe in the information that is broadcasted. Lita and

Cho (2012), emphasized the importance of frequency of broadcast in attitudinal change. In essence, the more media promote values, the more transformation takes place.

MEDIA USE IN NIGERIA

Media is the major means of dissemination of information in Nigeria which could be through electronic media, print media, and web media. Media use in Nigeria is very significant. Globally, consumers around the world spend an average of 463 minutes or over 7.5 hours per day with media (Watson, 2020). In Nigeria, according to a report by social media marketing platform “Hootsuite”, there are 98.39 million internet users in the country, of the 98.39 million Nigeria internet users, 54% access the internet on a daily basis. It was found out that 3 hours 17 minutes is the average amount of time Nigerians spend on social media which is higher than the global average of 3 hours 14 minutes. In Nigeria, all the thirty six states at least run one radio network and a television station as well as cable and Direct-to-home satellite offerings. July 2019, 122.7 million Nigerian were active internet users according to Nigerian Communications Commission.

Media is a powerful building block, it informs, entertains and educates the society; it reforms, reshapes, and raises voice against social evils. It is a watchdog for the society. It ignites awareness, moulds the people’s opinions and behaviour. It sets agenda for the society.

However, media use in Nigeria is majorly entertainment and politics not transforming the debilitated values (Kadiri, Muhammed, Raji, & Sulaiman, 2015). Scholars and critics have indicated that media are not fulfilling their functions and part of the areas in which they have failed is in giving adequate education that would ultimately change negatively oriented values. Even when disseminating news, the news according to Kadiri, Muhammed, Rji and Sulaiman (2015), is more of entertainment than information and education. The media often prefer to give sensational news that deals with sex, violence, fashion while downplaying the promotion of values including the core values, and good character. The lack of adequate information for building values have resulted in frustration, alienation and disorientation of the citizenry from contributing to the development and sustainability of the nation (Eboreime, 2008). Eboreime (2008), stated that media houses in Nigeria should change their focus to informing and enlightening the people.

CONCLUSION

The development and sustainability of a nation depends on the values the citizens hold. Values determine how honest, sincere, hardworking, courageous, peaceful, and accountable people are. Several studies (Asemah, Ekharefo & Olaniran, 20113; Njoku, 2015; Olaito, 2017) have indicated that people in Nigeria hold negative values such as dishonesty, insincerity, indolence, and conflict contrary to the national core values. Page (2018), stated that corruption is the single greatest obstacle preventing Nigeria from achieving its potential. According to him, corruption has drained billions of dollars from Nigerian economy yearly, stymied the development and weakened the relationships between the government and the citizens.

Ideally, every religious organisation promotes values and teaches people to live according to the precepts given by God who will judge all humans. Such precepts include love, justice, equality, peace, accountability, integrity, and honesty. Media also are expected to promote values and educate people using different approaches in order for every person, irrespective of status and level, to understand and imbibe the values

Religion and media are two powerful institutions that have been used to transform values in different places and times. In Nigeria however, the institutions are often used to promote negative values and focus on entertaining people to the detriment of the moral, intellectual and economic development of the people. Therefore, if the two institutions are used appropriately, values would be transformed in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Religious leaders in Nigeria should be concerned with value teaching rather than entertainment.
2. Religious leaders should ensure that values are inculcated into every activity in religious gathering. This requires that leaders set an example by eschewing vanity, extravagance, and frivolity in their personal lives.
3. Religious leaders should ensure that religious gatherings are organised to focus on the worship of God and learning his precepts rather than the celebration and hero worship of religious leaders.
4. Directors in media houses need to revamp the content of broadcasts, report and programs because “content is king”; if content is inspiring, transformation of values would occur and behaviours would change. Focus should not be on only entertainment.
5. Media regulatory bodies should formulate and implement policies that will discourage the promotion of ill-values as the current prevalent practices in media houses in Nigeria.

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